

What is the future of our profession? Imaginaries and life stories across three generations of women on-foot shellfish collectors in Galicia, Spain

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Abstract

The on-foot harvest of shellfish has been carried out by Galician women since time immemorial. Until the end of the last century, women of young age– mainly from low-income families - were brought to the beach by their mothers and grandmothers to be taught where, when and how to collect shellfish. Since the process of professionalization of this on-foot shellfish fishery during the 1990s, this activity has only been allowed to women (or men) in possession of a fishing license (permex in Spanish) which is only granted to people older than 18 years. The professionalization also brought about the implementation of a co-management regime following international standards for sustainable exploitation of marine resources and the establishment of women shellfish collectors' associations with certain level of participation in decision-making arenas. Despite these developments, the number of on-foot shellfish collectors in Galicia has been in decline over the last two decades. Hard working conditions and the low profitability associated with diminished catches, habitat deterioration and climate change might be contributing to this decline. This paper uses life stories of women on-foot shellfish collectors belonging to three different generations and assesses the extent to which their visions of the future of the profession are influenced by their experiences, identities and family traditions. Drawing on the concept of imaginaries as collective representations of a desired future, the paper examines the values and cultural changes that the advent of professionalization and sustainable development has had on this group of women in Galician traditional fishing communities.

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